

Data Management Plan ERC CoG NOTIMEFORCOSMO. n. 101126304

Project Acronym NOTIMEFORCOSMO

Project Number 101126304

Project Summary

The beginnings of the universe are encoded in the statistical properties of primordial perturbations imprinted at the hot Big Bang. Our understanding of primordial cosmology comes from measurements of these imprinted spatial correlations. They form a static pattern, and its apparent lack of causality is elegantly explained by an earlier period of time evolution. This time evolution from very primordial eras of the universe can not be observed directly. For conceptual and practical purposes, a reformulation of cosmological perturbation theory in which time is emergent is of fundamental importance. We hypothesize that there is an intrinsic description of primordial fluctuations that only uses their statistical properties and in which time emerges. Our approach has three steps. First, we propose a systematic development of the theory of "boundary differential equations" for cosmological correlation functions, and the development of new kinematical variables for cosmological correlators. With these tools in hand, we will calculate a large set of "theoretical data": cosmological correlations of many different particles, coming from a variety of early universe scenarios. With this data in hand, we will search for new principles from which time evolution emerges from the static distribution of cosmological perturbations. Having a reformulation of cosmological evolution with emergent time, a glimpse into the possible beginning of our universe might become accessible, as well as its imprint in cosmological correlations.

Dataset summary The data in this project consists of the following:

- Algebraic calculations to check and confirm the basic physical ideas in various projects. These are mostly done through handwritten notes—typically scanned and later digitized in scientific typesetting, through LateX—as well as on computer algebra programs. This data is kept stored in different forms. For "pencil and paper" calculations, the members of the project write notes that are kept in a shared folder, and are available to the PI and to the other members participating in a specific project. This type of data is not shared with other members of the group unless it becomes clear that it is important to them. The reason is that often times partial notes assume too much from the reader, are not presented in the most pedagogical way, and, being preliminary, might have mistakes. Nonetheless, we keep such records for future reference, having in mind that the mileage from old unpublished notes may vary. When it comes to data from computer algebra programs, it is also often kept in a shared folder, where all versions of notebooks etc. are saved. As Scuola Normale has access to a Microsoft OneDrive institutional subscription, backups of all files associated to the project will be saved there and remain easily accessible to group members.

- Publications which summarize the physics content of the findings of our project. They contain all necessary information for the conclusions to be reproduced by other researchers, both in the form of detailed instructions on how to compute the necessary formulas to reach similar conclusions to ours, as well as a thorough analysis of the consequences of these formulas. The physics papers tend to be written in a format that presents a long introduction to the topic; a summary of the main results in the paper; a list of notation, conventions etc. to help the reader navigate the formulas; then sections explaining in detail the various findings of our group. Finally we show appendices with extra technical details, that might be useful to the reader, but would make the main text very dry if added to the main narrative of the paper. The papers are freely available on the arXiv website, and are updated as often as necessary—sometimes even after being accepted for publication, if there is need to add further information to make the presentation clearer to the community.
- If there is computer code that is necessary to efficiently reproduce the results of the paper (e.g. it takes a long time to implement all the necessary computer algebra, optimize it etc.) then we add to the arXiv posting either a link to a github page or a Mathematica notebook as ancillary file to the arXiv posting. For most code produced by the project (mainly Mathematica files, which are the world standard for computer algebra in theoretical physics) the final products will also be submitted to Zenodo.

For reference, the papers published either by myself and/or by group members (all in bold below) are

1. D. Baumann, G. Mathys, **G. L. Pimentel** and F. Rost, “A new twist on spinning (A)dS correlators,” JHEP **01**, 202 (2025) [arXiv:2408.02727 [hep-th]]
2. C. Fevola, **G. L. Pimentel**, A. L. Sattelberger and **T. Westerdijk**, “Algebraic Approaches to Cosmological Integrals,” to appear in Le Matematiche, [arXiv:2410.14757 [math.AG]].
3. G. Compère, S. J. Hoque and **E. Ş. Kutluk**, “The $SO(1,4)$ flux-balance laws of de Sitter at quadrupolar order,” [arXiv:2411.16215 [gr-qc]].
4. C. Beetar, M. Carrillo González, **S. Jaitly** and T. Keseman, “Double Copy in AdS3 from Minitwistor Space,” [arXiv:2410.23342 [hep-th]].

FAIR data and resources

1. Making data findable

As mentioned above, all data is available to the PI (internal notebooks, partial notes, computer algebra, etc.) through shared folders with the coauthors of various papers, and to the public through arXiv postings and publications in Open Access journals. The papers can be easily found through the public profiles of the PI on INSPIRE-HEP and Google Scholar.

2. Making data openly accessible

The data is openly accessible on the profiles of the PI through the arXiv preprints available, and all publications will be in CC-BY (as well as the future arXiv submissions from the project). The main journals where we will submit most of the publications are part of SCOAP³, an open source consortium that supports those journals, and for which Scuola Normale also contributes.

3. Making data interoperable

Manuscripts are written in English and describe the results in plenty of detail to make them easily reproducible. The literature is written in extended form hence easy to find on the web.

4. Increase data reuse

No embargo will be applied. All data will remain indefinitely open access. The data will remain accessible on arXiv and INSPIRE-HEP and will be available as an open access publication in journals.

5. Allocation of resources and data security

At this stage, all publications are submitted to journals that publish Open Access free of charge. For example, in theoretical physics, Italy participates (with contributions from Scuola Normale) in SCOAP³, a consortium that makes all publications in JHEP free of charge for the authors. Moreover, data will be managed through shared Dropbox folders. This might be revisited later, depending on the progress of the various work packages of the project.